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Typology of Cattle Maintenance System in Sangbintang Area, Bolaang Mongondow North Regency

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the characteristics of beef cattle breeders and the typology of beef cattle breeding systems in the Sangbintang area of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, conducted from January to June 2018. This study uses a survey method with data analysis, namely: Quantitative descriptive to identify the characteristics of beef cattle breeders and typology of beef cattle rearing systems in the Sangbintang area of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, through data tabulation. The results showed that characteristics of breeders in the Sangbintang area in general are: low educated (elementary level), average productive age is 15-65 years, the number of dependents of families is moderate, namely 3-4 people, the experience of raising beef cattle is quite long namely 6-10 years. While the typology of beef cattle rearing systems consists of 5 (five), namely: 1) the system of moving care/extensive (67.39%), 2) the cage system, sleeping / intensive (11.96%), 3). Cage, loose, semi-intensive (10.87%) system, 4) loose/semi-intensive (4.38%) cage system, and traditional, feed/traditional (5.43%) system. From the aspect of typology, this maintenance system illustrates that most are still traditional and extensive; this affects the development of cattle population and body weight in the period of rearing.

Keywords: *beef cattle, characteristics, maintenance typology, sangbintang region*

PRELIMINARY

Animal Husbandry is one of the sub-sectors that play a role in contributing to agricultural development. Livestock development as part of agricultural development will be related to the reorientation of agricultural development policies. Further animal husbandry development is closely related to the development of an area. Livestock development, in this case, must also be able to synergize with the objectives of rural area development. The development of rural areas is meant to improve the standard of social and economic life of the community. Rural area development can be achieved through the development of rural-based potential areas as centers of growth.

The livestock sub-sector is an important part of community life in the North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, besides agriculture. Animal husbandry is a place where livestock can grow and develop from breeding, raising to fattening. The livestock subsector in realizing the livestock development program operationally begins with the formation or structuring of the area through an agribusiness system and business approach. Development of animal husbandry and animal health, in this case, is development that emphasizes the relationship between objects (livestock) and subjects (breeder farmers).

Development in the livestock sub-sector plays a role in improving the quality of human resources in a sustainable manner. Animal husbandry development has a very good and promising role in the future. This phenomenon is caused because the demand for materials derived from livestock tends to increase. The increase occurred along with an increase in population, income and increased public awareness in consuming highly nutritious food.

Livestock resources, in this case, is an important component in a farming system in various places in Indonesia, including in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency. The problem of the livestock sector at this time is the inability to optimally provide livestock products to meet the nutritional needs of the community for animal protein.

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Livestock in Bolaang Mongondow Utara Regency not only serves as a source of household income but also as savings that can be sold at any time if the community needs money. Livestock, in this case, acts as a source of animal protein from livestock in an effort to improve the intelligence of human resources. The development of the livestock commodity population in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency has increased from year to year. The population of beef cattle in 2011 was 12,490 individuals, and in 2016 there were 14,690 animals. This shows that the development of beef cattle currently has shown a serious development (Department of Agriculture Kab. Bolmut, 2016)

The Government of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency in 2013 through the Regional Development Planning Agency has compiled the Integrated Livestock Agribusiness Master Plan for Beef Cattle Development Areas, which is directed at three sub-districts as the concentration of development, namely Sangkub District, Bintauna District and Bolangitang Timur District. The number of beef cattle in the Sangbintang region is 8,479, consisting of 3,265 Sangkub Districts, 2,968 Bintauna Districts and 2,246 East Bolangitang Districts, (Agriculture Service District, Bolmut, 2016). This illustrates that the policy of developing beef cattle farms in the North Bolaang Mongondow Regency is directed at the development of an integrated area that is designated as the "Sangbintang" area.

Various problems in the development of cattle farms in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, including the high productive slaughtering, small-scale business for each breeder and are generally still limited to side businesses with traditional maintenance systems. The reality on the ground shows that only a small proportion of farmers make cattle business as their main business. The scale of a part-time cattle business is certainly less competitive in the business world. This condition shows that cattle breeding business in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency will be unable to compete with other regions in North Sulawesi. Another problem is the limited capital of farmers so that they are not motivated to develop their livestock businesses. Efforts that can be made are policies that need to be made in relation to investment in cattle farming. Weak institutions are also a problem in the development of cattle farms in this area. The institutional weaknesses are mainly at the level of cattle farmer groups. Another thing that is also a problem in animal husbandry development is the lack of available food resources for cattle. These problems are causing the development of cattle population in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency rather slowly.

The North Bolaang Mongondow District Government has launched a cattle introduction policy to encourage an increase in cattle population. Other policies include government cooperation with other regions (North Gorontalo District and Buol District), universities (Gorontalo State University) and experts from the Netherlands. This collaboration is known as North-North cooperation implemented since 2016. The policy was launched by the government for the introduction of technology in an effort to encourage the development of the cattle population beef.

Bolaang Mongondow Utara, as one of the districts in North Sulawesi, has considerable potential in developing beef cattle farms. But in general, beef cattle farms are people's farms. Farms generally implement traditional maintenance systems by utilizing human resources and available feed resources. The profile of smallholder farms shows that, most of the cattle raised by small-scale farmers with limited land and capital, using local breeds, cattle are kept by grazing on agricultural land or under coconut trees, cage waste management and disease control are not appropriate with the suggested and livestock breeding still naturally, the technology used is simple, not yet fully market oriented and not sensitive to changes. They are based on the condition of the profile of these smallholder farms so that the production and productivity of cattle are low. The situation ultimately affects the income of farmers and the development of cattle in the study area. The question is how is the typology of beef cattle breeding systems and the characteristics of beef cattle breeders in the Sangbintang beef cattle breeding area of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency if the business is categorized as a community farm.

UPDATE / NOVELTY

1. The novelty of the aspects of the method, where this study uses a simple method that is quantitative descriptive, with a comprehensive approach such as surveys, observations, direct field observations, interviews, so that the results of the study are in-depth.

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- The novelty of the aspects of the research results is the identification of local characteristics of breeders and typology of beef cattle rearing systems, specifically in the Sangbintang area of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Location Determination Method

This research will be conducted in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency using survey methods. The approach used in this research is a quantitative approach. Determination of the location of the District in North Bolaang Mongondow District was done intentionally (*purposive sampling*), namely Sangkub District, Bintauna District and East Bolangitang District .

2. Sample Determination Method

The method of determining the sample in this study was taken by *purposive sampling*, which was selected 3 Districts from 6 Subdistricts in Bolaang Mongondow Utara Regency, which were designated as beef cattle development areas (sangbintang) , are samples that represent the population. The number of respondent farmers was determined using the *proportionate sampling* method using the following Slovin formula

Note: n = sample

N = Population

e = the error rate / error (*error*) received (10%) Thus obtained the following calculation:

$$1,106$$

$$n = \frac{1,106}{1 + 1,106} = 91,71 \text{ or rounded up to } 92 \text{ farmers}$$

$$1 + 1,106 (0,1)^2$$

Table 1. The population and sample of beef cattle farmers in each district

No .	sub-district	Village	Animal Population (Tail)	Breeder (People)	Sample
1	Sangkub	Sidodadi	325	142	12
		Tombolango	332	185	15
		Pangkusa	293	102	8
2	Bintauna	Pimpi	215	108	9
		Bintauna	209	107	9
		Padang	204	96	8
3	East Bolangitan	Biontong	316	171	14
		Binjeita	208	94	8
		Bohabak	207	101	8
Total			2309	1106	92

Source :: Agricultural Service processed, Data 2016

3. Data Collection Method

The type of data used is *cross-section* data and *time-series* data, from primary data sources and secondary data. Primary data (*cross-section a year*) obtained from direct interviews with respondents. While secondary data (*annual time series*) were obtained from the agencies associated with this study and published research data. Data collection techniques are interviews with farmers and direct observations in the field.

4. Analysis Methods

The data analysis method used in this study was carried out in the following stages:

4.1. Identification Typology Maintenance System of Beef Cattle

The method used to analyze the typology of the Beef Cattle Maintenance System is to use qualitative descriptive analysis with survey methods, observations, direct observations in the field and interviews with respondents with the questionnaire given. The results of the analysis are contained in tables and or diagrams. Typology of beef cattle farms, analyzed based on the scale of business and the level of income of farmers, namely: a) Beef cattle as a sideline business, with a level of income from beef cattle business less than 30%, b) Beef cattle as a business branch, where farmer farmers try mixed farming with beef cattle, the amount of income from the beef cattle business 30-70%, 3) raise beef cattle as the main business, where the cattle farmer is to try beef cattle as the main business and other agricultural commodities as a side business, with a beef cattle business income level of 70-100%, 4) Beef cattle as an industrial business, where the commodity of beef cattle is cultivated specifically with a beef cattle business income level of 100%. The typology of beef cattle business is also analyzed based on the ownership of livestock, the level of production, the technology used and the number of products marketed.

4.2. Identification of Beef Cattle Farmer Characteristics

The method used to analyze the characteristics of Peter son of Beef is by using a quantitative descriptive analysis survey method, observation, direct field observation and interviews with respondents to the questionnaire given. The results of the analysis are contained in tables and or diagrams. Characteristics of beef cattle breeders, based on the age of the breeders, the level of education of the breeders, the area of land controlled, the length of experience of raising beef cattle, and the number of dependents of the family.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typology of Beef Cattle Maintenance Systems in Sangbintang District, North

Bolaang Mongondow Regency

There are 3 (three) systems for raising cattle that are commonly carried out, namely: (i) grazing systems; (ii) cut and carry system, and (iii) combination system (livestock grazing in limited areas and forage feed shortages are provided in cages, while Santoso et al. (2012) classify in 4 typologies, namely: 1) Cattle farming beef cattle as a part-time business, income from livestock business is less than 30%, 2) beef cattle farming as a branch of business, income from beef cattle business 30-70%, 3) beef cattle farming as the main business, beef cattle business revenue 70- 100%, and 4) beef cattle farming as an industrial business, where the commodity of beef cattle is cultivated specifically with a beef cattle business income level of 100%.

In this study, researchers looked at typologies from aspects of beef cattle breeding systems by 92 respondents. In this study in the area of SangBintang beef cattle production centers identified 5 (five) typology classifications, namely: 1) The system of raising cattle is constantly being fed with feeding, drinking in a cage, 2) The system of raising cattle is placed in cages, but cattle are released in the grazing land, breeders provide food and drink in a cage 3) cattle raising system by tying cattle in grazing land on a nomadic basis, 4) Cattle raising system is sheltered, but cattle are released in the grazing land , 5) the system of raising cattle by tying cattle in grazing lands by moving, and fed and drinking. As shown in the following table.

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Table. 26. Typology Maintenance System KSP Cattle in the b intang, 2018.

No	Typology	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Tie moved	62	67,39
2	impounded	11	11.96
3	Cage, loose	4	4,38
4	Cage, loose, feed	10	10.87
5	Tie, feed	5	5.43
	total	92	100.00

Source: Primary data processed results, 2018.

Table 26. shows that the typology of cattle maintenance systems by tying cattle in nomadic grazing lands was 67.39%. Furthermore, typology of cattle maintenance system is kept continuously by feeding, drinking in cages as much as 11.96%, cattle maintenance system is suspended, but cattle are released in grazing land, breeders provide food and drink in a stable, as much as 10, 87%, typology of cattle raising systems by tying cattle in grazing lands by moving, and fed and drinking, as much as 5.43%, and typologies of raising cattle systems are anchored, but cattle are released in the fields pastoralism, as much as 4.38% .

a. Typology system of maintenance of connective sedentary

This typology of cattle maintenance systems has a very large percentage in the Sangbintang Region, which is 67.39%. Most farmers raise their cattle in this way. Where the farmer brings his cattle every day to the grazing area, the grazing area can be owned or owned by someone else, in the form of agricultural land that is bero (not planted), or other areas that are not utilized or idle lands, then cattle in tie in the middle of the grass as well as feed the cow. The length of the ox is 15-25 meters, with the aim of the cow being able to graze freely. Day farmers generally move their cattle ties 1-2 times to other places where there are grass and shelter for the night. The need to drink cattle is less of a concern, especially as livestock diseases that often attack cattle are not well controlled. The results of identification with the farmers stated that the basic reasons for raising cattle with a moving bundle system are: 1) hereditary habits, 2) making it easy to keep cattle, 3) no need for permanent labor, 5) keeping cattle as a side business, 5) raising cows as savings, 6) cows as labor helps keepers in agricultural and non-agricultural activities.

b. Typology of maintenance and binding system

This typology of cattle maintenance systems has a very small percentage in the Sangbintang region of 5.43%. Where breeders carry cattle every day to the grazing land. The results of identification are generally grazing land, which is actually not grazing land but can be said as a shelter for cattle because in that place there is not enough grass for cattle, but in the prioritization of shade trees for cattle shelter. So that farmers provide food and drinks for the adequacy of livestock feed and drink needs. Cow cows are generally not far from the farmer's house. The results of identification with farmers stated that the basic reasons for raising cattle with this system are: 1) there is no need to make a cage, so it is more efficient, 2) cattle are easy to control because they are close to the dwellers' dwelling, 3) side businesses, but farmers have felt the contribution of livestock is large to the needs of the family, 4) cattle power can be reached immediately if needed suddenly.

c. Typology of cage and detachment maintenance systems

This typology of cattle maintenance systems has a very small percentage in the Sangbintang Region which is 4.38%. Where breeders make cages, but the function of the cage is solely for shelter or sleep at night, because cattle are removed every morning from the cage and brought back to the cage at night. In the cage

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there is no supply of forage or other food and there is no drink for cattle. Cattle are released, but the mother cows are tied to the grass so that other cows are not far from the mother. The basic reason for maintaining this system is the low cost (efficiency) and easy implementation (effectiveness) of raising cattle. From the standpoint of the maintenance of cattle, of course this system is not good because it does not heed the business of beef cattle, namely: superior breeds, feed, housing, health, breeding, management and marketing.

d. Typology of cage, detachment and feed maintenance systems

The typology of this cattle breeding system has a small percentage in the Sangbintang region, which is no more than 10.87%. Where the cattle at the time of the evening are kept in a cage, while in the morning until the afternoon is removed from the cage to graze on the pasture. Every night, farmers provide cattle feed in the form of mixed-grass with varying amounts depending on the results of obtaining grass and the needs of the cattle. If the cattle get enough grass during the day, then feed is less at night, but if during the day they get insufficient grass feed, then feed at night is added, but also depends on the acquisition of breeder feed. In the typology of this maintenance system, breeders already understand the advantages and disadvantages of raising beef cattle, but do not understand the effects of animal feed and health on the weight gain of cattle that are kept. Farmers' perceptions are based on a count if the animals that are kept are given enough food and drink, then their weight will increase in line with the age of the raised cattle. The basic reasons for breeders to implement this system are: 1) mixed-grass in rural areas is still sufficiently available, 2) There are no regulations from the district, sub-district or village governments that prohibit the release of cattle, 3) save on feed costs, and 4) livestock health can controlled when the cow is anchored.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussion, the following conclusions are obtained:

- a. Characteristics of breeders in the area of Sangbintang beef cattle development are: Generally, the elementary school education (48.91%), the highest percentage of breeders is 15-65 years of age 95.65%), meaning that the breeders in the Sangintang area are productive. From the aspect of dependents the most families are 3-4 people (66.30%), the category of medium households, From the aspect of the length of raising the majority of beef cattle is 6-10 years (32.61%), and most aspects of land ownership are > 1-2 ha (48.91%). From this aspect of breeders' characteristics, it illustrates that in general breeders still have the potential to be developed.
- b. Typology of beef cattle breeding systems in the Sangbintang beef cattle development Center area was obtained 5 (five), namely: 1) moving bundle system (67.39%), 2) cage, sleeping systems (11.96%), 3) The cage, loose, feed system (10.87%), 4) the cage, feed system (5.43%) and the loose cage system (4.38%). With a typology of a maintenance system like this, of course, meat production is not as expected. So that in the development of the Sangbintang area, it is necessary to increase breeders' resources in terms of beef cattle cultivation, with the hope that the breeders will shift their maintenance system to a sleeping cage system and a stable, loose, feed system, because these two systems can be categorized in semi-intensive and intensive businesses, while the other systems are classified as traditional and extensive business.

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